

Introduction to International Open Science Organizations: RDA and ESIP

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LAND ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to acknowledge the Traditional Owners of the lands, seas and waters of the areas that I live, work and meet on.

I acknowledge their continuing connection to their culture and pay my respects to their Elders past, present and future.

'Gadi' by Lynnice Church for
NCI Australia 2020

Outline

- Review the work of the Belmont e-Infrastructures and Data Management Project 2013 to 2016, in particular its aim to develop eInfrastructures and global data management research infrastructures for Global Change Research
- Discuss why it is important to work internationally in the Open Science community
- Introduce you to the:
 - Research Data Alliance
 - Earth Science Information Partners
 - GEO
 - CODATA
- Ask a thought provoking question of you all at the end of my presentation

A bigger picture, beyond PARSEC, beyond Belmont

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

We have grand challenges that all Earth and environmental science data can contribute to beyond our project, but....

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There are limits on sharing data globally

- Remember: **the size of the community that can programmatically exchange any data information is only as large as the size of the community that could read and understand the same standard.**
- Increasingly to solve global challenges of today:
 - digital data collections need to be re-used and re-purposed by much broader communities
 - data need to be accessed machine readable formats
- Globally agreed standards for the representation of Earth and environmental science information are fundamental to allowing programmatic sharing of data both within and beyond any domain.

Current and Future State: an example from OneGeochemistry

Current State: Multiple human readable systems, some with metadata: some are FAIR but only within their system.

Developing State: Some systems attempting to harmonise, but still only human readable systems: no globally agreed community standards. Findable and Accessible, but not Interoperable or Reusable.

Future State: A global framework made of multiple machine actionable systems, each compliant with globally agreed community standards and **all FAIR to both humans and machines**

We need the silos to come together, but how?

The lessons of history in building infrastructures: one size will never fit all

Power sockets of the world

(<https://www.power-plugs-sockets.com/>)

Railway gauges of the world

(https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/1/1f/Rail_gauge_world.png)

Our Starting Premises are:

<https://www.redbubble.com/i/ipad-case/One-Size-Fits-All-by-JCorbettcartoon/23369092.MNKGF>

1. In any infrastructure, one size does not fit all
2. The size of the community that can programmatically exchange any data information is only as large as the size of the community that could read and understand the same standard.

In the beginning.....

- As the Belmont Forum was already funding research in support of better understanding of global change, in early 2013 they recognized the need for a more coordinated approach to the information being generated by this research, in support of the Future Earth agenda.
- A group of experts were nominated by the different funders to develop a Community Strategy and Implementation Plan (CSIP) for the development of the necessary e-infrastructures and data management regimes to support Belmont and Future Earth.

<https://council.science/publications/future-earth-2025-vision-2/>

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A place to stand was informed by a Survey

- A Belmont Forum Open Data Survey was made available online from September to November 2014: 1330 responses.
- Dissemination channels targeted researchers, data scientists, data managers and technologists from the environmental sciences, earth sciences, marine and polar sciences, biodiversity, as well as equivalents in the social and economic sciences.
- The survey aimed to seek information on:
 - Key open data activities in various communities dealing with global environmental change to identify leading examples of best practice from a user perspective;
 - Areas where users' desire to share could be enhanced by new/other developments; and
 - Identifying barriers to "open data sharing" from a user perspective (as either a data provider or data user).

Open Data in Global Environmental Research: The Belmont Forum's Open Data Survey

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Abstract

This paper presents the findings of the Belmont Forum's survey on Open Data which targeted the global environmental research and data infrastructure community. It highlights users' perceptions of the term "open data", expectations of infrastructure functionalities, and barriers and enablers for the sharing of data. A wide range of good practice examples was pointed out by the respondents which demonstrates a substantial uptake of data sharing through e-infrastructures and a further need for enhancement and consolidation. Among all policy responses, funder policies seem to be the most important motivator. This supports the conclusion that stronger mandates will strengthen the case for data sharing.

Introduction

The Belmont Forum, a group of high-level representatives from major funding agencies across the globe, coordinates funding for collaborative research actions to address the challenges and opportunities of global environmental change. To collaboratively develop capable e-infrastructures to meet the data arising from the Belmont Challenge and the Future Earth agenda, a multi-phased E-Infrastructure and Data Management Collaborative Research Action (CRA) was initiated in late 2013. This was given the task to develop a strategy and implementation plan to further shape strategic science policies, outlining what can be done better, in a multilateral way, to fund and support global environmental change research. Note that this CRA was only focussed on defining possible actions in support of this agenda—the Belmont Forum will need to decide which actions it is able to support.

A survey, developed by the Belmont Forum working group on open data (one of 6 working groups under this CRA) invited researchers of various science communities, interested laypersons, government employees, and others who are providing and/or using open data in the scope of global environmental change, or are planning/interested in doing so in the future, to share their views and experiences on data publishing, access and (re)use. The main aim was to learn more about:

- Key open data activities in various communities dealing with global environmental change to identify leading examples of best practice from a user perspective;

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1/29

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Results of Survey

1. Funders should make open data archiving mandatory.
2. Scientific merits as well as accelerating research and applications are still the main motivators for publishing data.
3. Support and training activities should be backed in concerted ways, targeting researchers as well as current and future data and information professionals.
4. Interoperability between infrastructures should be further facilitated. Interoperability should take into account generic requirements (e.g. providing links to publications and funder information) as well as disciplinary norms and standards (e.g. vocabularies, metadata standards).

Schmidt B, Gemeinholzer B, Treloar A (2016) Open Data in Global Environmental Research: The Belmont Forum's Open Data Survey. PLoS ONE 11(1): e0146695. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0146695>

Final Report: A Place to Stand Recommendations

Developed 5 recommendations:

1. **Adopt Data Principles** that establish a global interoperable data e-infrastructure with cost-effective solutions for widening access to data and ensuring its long-term preservation;
2. **Foster communication, collaboration and coordination** with *the wider community* and across Belmont Forum projects and initiatives through establishing a Data and e-Infrastructure Coordination Office;
3. **Promote good data planning and stewardship in all Belmont Forum agency-funded research**, enabling harmonization of e-infrastructure through enhanced project data planning, monitoring, review and sharing;
4. **Demonstrate international best and common practice, and inform Belmont Forum research e- infrastructure policy**, in harmony with the evolving research practices and digital ecosystem; and
5. **Support the development of a cross-disciplinary training curriculum to expand human capacity** in data-aware technology and data-intensive analysis methods for Environmental Science.

The recommendations:

1. Could be put into practice by research funders; and
2. Provide a way for research funders to move towards a greater level of international standardization in policy and practice

<https://zenodo.org/record/34370#.Yzq2EIJBy7I>

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Introducing the Research Data Alliance

- Was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 by the European Commission, the United States Government's National Science Foundation and National Institute of Standards and Technology, and the Australian National Data Service with the goal of building the social and technical infrastructure to enable open sharing and re-use of globally.
- Has over 10,000 members from 145 countries.
- RDA provides a neutral space where its members can come together to develop and adopt infrastructure that promotes data-sharing and data-driven research.
- Holds hybrid plenaries twice a year: the next one is 21-23 March, 2023 in Gotheberg, Sweden.

The screenshot shows the Research Data Alliance website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for RDA EU, RDA US, CONTACT US, LOGOUT, and SUPPORT. Below this is a header section with the RDA logo and several statistics: 'O&A Members' (71), 'MY PROFILE' (Members: 12866), and 'RDA Groups' (WG & IGs: 100). A main banner features a large '10' logo with the RDA globe inside, celebrating 'A Decade of Data: Celebrating 10 Years of the Research Data Alliance'. Below the banner, there is a section titled 'RDA STATEMENT ON UKRAINE:' which reads: 'The Research Data Alliance is a global organization with over 12,400 members from 145 countries, and is built on principles that include openness, inclusivity and transparency. The Council is the main governing body of RDA, and would like to express its concern and sympathy for our colleagues and fellow researchers in Ukraine, as we join other organizations across the international research community in calling for a quick and peaceful resolution to the crisis.' Below the statement, there are sections for 'NEWS & EVENTS' and 'FOLLOW US'. The 'NEWS & EVENTS' section features an article titled 'Principios FAIR en el gestión de las investigacion...' dated 21/10/2022. The 'FOLLOW US' section shows a tweet from @resdatall about a webinar.

<https://rd-alliance.org/>

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RDA works “bottom-up” through groups

- RDA directly and logically tackles numerous data infrastructure challenges through the work of:
 - ~ 43 Working Groups;
 - ~60 Interest Groups; and
 - Communities of Practice, Coordination Groups.
- Covers all disciplines from science, humanities and social sciences, health, agriculture, and more.
- Currently is free to join.
- Just about any topic is covered in building data and software infrastructures and if it is not there, then go and form a group yourself!

Building the social and technical bridges to enable open sharing and re-use of data

RDA EU RDA US CONTACT US LOGOUT SUPPORT

RDA RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

O&A Members 71
Active Organisational & Affiliate members

MY PROFILE Members: 12866
My details, My Groups, My comments
[Go to my profile](#)

RDA Groups WG & IGs: 100
Discover what RDA Working and Interest Groups and all other Groups are up to and find out how to join them. [Explore Groups](#)

ABOUT RDA GET INVOLVED GROUPS RECOMMENDATIONS & OUTPUTS RDA FOR DISCIPLINES PLENARIES & EVENTS NEWS & MEDIA

Interest Groups

Home » Groups » Interest Groups

Group Title	Chair(s)
Active Data Management Plans IG	rda-datamanagplans@rda-groups.org David Giaretta, Kevin Ashley, Tomasz Miksa, Elli Papadopoulou, Maria Praetzelis
Archives and Records Professionals for Research Data IG	Rebecca Grant, Laura Molloy, Sarah Ramdeen, Hea Lim Rhee
Biodiversity Data Integration IG	rda-biodivdataintegr-ig@rda-groups.org Wouter Addink, Hamish Holewa, Sridhar Gutam, Libby Ellwood
Chemistry Research Data IG	chemistry-research-data@rda-groups.org Leah McEwen, Stuart Chalk, Ian Bruno
CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries	Hugh Shanahan, Bianca Peterson, Raphael Cbe, Sara El jadid
Data Conservation IG	conservation@rda-groups.org Denise Hills, Stephen Diggs
Data Discovery Paradigms IG	datadiscovery@rda-groups.org Mingfang Wu, Fotis Psomopoulos, Kathleen Gregory
Data Economics IG	data-economics-ig@rda-groups.org Yuri Demchenko, Jane Greenberg
Data for Development IG	Ingvill Constanze Mochmann, Norman Mukasa, Robert Sentamu, Mahadia Tunga, Agapiti Manday

Creating and Managing RDA Groups

- Creating or joining an RDA Working Group
- WG Case Statement Process
- Creating or Joining a Community of Practice
- Creating or Joining an RDA Interest Group
- Group Chairs: Roles and Responsibilities
- Initiate New Group
- Birds of a Feather
- Find a Group

All Groups

- Working Groups
- Interest Groups
- Historical Groups
- Coordination Groups
- National Groups
- Communities of Practice

Introducing the Earth Space and Environmental Sciences Interest Group (ESES-IG)

- Co-Chairs are Shelley Stall (AGU, USA), Pedro Corrêa (Universidade de Sao Paulo, Brazil), Danie Kincaide (Woods Hole, USA), Helen Glaves (BGS, UK), Lesley Wyborn (ANU, Australia).
- Meets to spread the word on ESES projects anywhere.
- We maintain two catalogues:
 - A [Data Infrastructure Catalogue](#) of groups building systems anywhere in the world; and
 - A [Semantic Resources Catalogue](#) which lists vocabularies, ontologies, semantic models relevant to ESES.
- Please add your projects and resources to these catalogues.
- Please contact us if you would like to highlight your project at our next plenary.

The screenshot shows the website for the ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences Interest Group (IG). The page has a green header with navigation links: RDA EU, RDA US, CONTACT US, LOGOUT, SUPPORT. Below the header is a breadcrumb trail: Home » Working and Interest Groups » Interest Group » ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG. The main content area features a green bar with the group name and a 'Taxonomy' section. Below this are several icons representing different functions: Posts, Create Wiki index, Events, Repository, Outputs, Charter, Plenaries, and Members. A 'create new content' button is also present. The group status is 'IG Established' with a green checkmark icon. There are 'View', 'Edit', and 'Group' buttons. A notice states: 'Please make sure the group follows the new RDA Groups Policy, which came into effect on 1 April 2021. Please contact enquiries[at]rd-alliance.org if you have any questions.' Below this is a box containing group details: Status: Recognised & Endorsed; Chair (s): Helen Glaves, Danie Kinkade, Shelley Stall, Pedro Corrêa, Lesley Wyborn; Group Email: eses-ig@rda-groups.org; Secretariat Liaison: enquiries@rd-alliance.org; TAB Liaison: Mingfang Wu. At the bottom of the box, there is a paragraph describing the group's mission and a paragraph about its history.

Join us on <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/esiprda-earth-space-and-environmental-sciences-ig>

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Earth Systems Information Partners - ESIP

- ESIP is a community of >120 partner organizations and volunteers.
- We work together to meet environmental data challenges.
- Similar to RDA, but focused on Earth and environmental sciences
- Is sponsored by the USGS, NASA, NOAA
- Works through 28 clusters and 6 committees: [full list is here](#)

ABOUT ▾ NEWS & EVENTS ▾ PROGRAMS ▾ RESOURCES ▾ GET INVOLVED ▾

Earth Science Data for All People

Join a Telecon

Earth Science
Information Partners
(ESIP)

At ESIP, we believe society's quality of life, economic opportunities, and stewardship of the planet are enhanced by regular use of scientifically sound Earth science data and information provided in a timely manner by a community that is collaborating to improve their collective services.

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Other International Groups: Geo

- GEO (Group on Earth Observations)
 - GEO is a partnership of more than 100 national governments and in excess of 100 Participating Organizations.
 - GEO is creating a Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) to better integrate observing systems and share data by connecting existing infrastructures using common standards.
 - GEO has more than 400 million open data resources in GEOSS from >150 national and regional providers.

The image shows a screenshot of the GEO Week 2022 website. At the top left is the logo for the Group on Earth Observations. To the right are social media icons for Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and Instagram. The main banner is orange and features the text "GEO WEEK 2022" in large, bold letters, followed by the tagline "Global Action for Local Impact" and the dates "31 October - 04 November 2022 | Accra, Ghana". On the right side of the banner is a colorful, abstract graphic. Below the banner, there is a section titled "Latest News & Blog Posts" with six small image thumbnails. To the right of this section is a "Faces of GEO" section featuring a portrait of Maria del Pilar Lorenza Rodriguez and a quote about the importance of Earth observations. Below that is a "Country Profiles" section with a world map and the text "COUNTRY PROFILES".

Other International Groups: CODATA

- CODATA (Committee on Data of the International Science Council)
- CODATA's strategic activities are divided into four priorities:
 1. Decadal Programme 'Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges' and the Global Open Science Cloud Initiative;
 2. Data Policy: promoting principles, policies and practices for FAIR;
 3. Data Science: advancing the frontiers of the science of data; and
 4. Data Skills: building capacity for Open Science by improving data skills and the functions of national science systems needed to support open data.

International FAIR Convergence Symposium 2022
Leiden, 24 - 26 October 2022

Panel Session at DCMI conference: The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework: Coordinating Standards for Scalable, Practical FAIR Sharing (4 October, 13:15 EDT)
Oct 4, 2022 | News
Tuesday, 4 October, 13:15-14:45 EDT The 20th International Conference on Dublin Core and Metadata Applications (DCMI 2022) Register here (virtual session): <https://www.dublincore.org/conferences/2022/sessions/panel-cross-domain-interoperability-framework/> We are now...
[read more](#)

Register now: DDI Controlled Vocabularies, the CESSDA Workbench, SKOS and XKOS
Oct 3, 2022 | News
Weds 12 October, 14:00-15:30 UTC Register here: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/84481111111> Controlled vocabularies are an important form of metadata, and are used for a broad range of purposes. This webinar looks at how controlled...
[read more](#)

Tweets from @CODATANews

C... Oct 4

Panel Session at DCMI conference: The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework: Coordinating Standards for Scalable, Practical FAIR Sharing (4 October, 13:15 EDT) [codata.org/panel-session-...](#) [#codata](#) [#FAIRdata](#) [#OpenScience](#)

WorldFAIR Project: Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice

Funded by the EU Horizon Europe Framework Programme, project call HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-01

Led by CODATA, with RDA as a major partner

The project comprises a global consortium of 19 partners from Africa, Australasia, Europe, and North and South America and features 11 case studies in a range of research disciplines:

1. Chemistry
2. Nanomaterials
3. Geochemistry
4. Social Surveys Data
5. Population Health
6. Urban Health
7. Biodiversity case study
8. Agriculture use case
9. Implementing FAIR in the Ocean Data and Information System
10. Disaster Risk Reduction
11. Cultural Heritage

The WorldFAIR Project will

- Introduce usage of [FAIR Implementation Profiles](#) to increase machine readability of data.
- Contribute to Global Interdisciplinary projects such e.g.:
 1. UN Sustainable Development Goals; and
 2. International Science Council Decadal Program 'Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges.
- Test the emerging idea of a Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework that will better enable transdisciplinary data-sharing.
- Still allow for deep scientific research and innovation within individual disciplines.

The 11 WorldFAIR case studies are grouped around 5 cognate areas:

1. Chemistry (WP3),
Nanomaterials (WP4)
Geochemistry (WP5)
2. Social surveys (WP6)
Demographic health & clinical research (WP7)
Urban health (WP8)
3. Biodiversity (WP9)
Agriculture (WP10)
4. Ocean Science/Sustainable Development (WP11)
Disaster Risk Reduction (WP12)
5. Cultural Heritage (WP13)

The limits on sharing data

- Remember: **the size of the community that can programmatically exchange any data information is only as large as the size of the community that could read and understand the same standard.**
- Increasingly to solve global challenges of today:
 - digital data collections need to be re-used and re-purposed by much broader communities
 - data need to be accessed machine readable formats
- Globally agreed standards for the representation of Earth and environmental science information are fundamental to allowing programmatic sharing of data both within and beyond any domain.

And now for that question I said I would ask...

- The original aim of the Belmont e-Infrastructures and Data Management Project was that Data and Information any Belmont project would be part of a global eInfrastructure and data management system
- The question is *“if data and information from PARSEC is integrating together, is it also contributing to the rapidly emerging global Earth and environmental Infrastructures developing within and beyond the Belmont Forum?”*
- Integrating beyond current project boundaries can be very challenging!

Landsat-8 image courtesy of the U.S. Geological Survey

